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Alina O. Musiienko –

Postgraduate Student of the European Union Law Department,
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University
(77 Hryhoriia Skovorody Street, 61024 Kharkiv)
<http://orcid.org/0009-0007-7380-4690>

NATO-EU Cooperation: the Euro-Atlantic Security Dilemma

У статті порушується низка питань, які виправдовують подальшу аналітичну взаємодію між Європейським Союзом та Організацією Північноатлантичного договору (НАТО). Наводиться певне історичне підґрунтя, щоб сформувати дискусію, і при цьому також описати еволюцію становлення та розвитку відносин НАТО з Європейським Союзом. Проаналізовано найбільш важливі аспекти співробітництва НАТО з Європейським Союзом у XXI столітті. Зроблено висновок про існування тенденції до поглиблення і розширення співробітництва НАТО з Європейським Союзом в питаннях забезпечення миру і безпеки в Європі. Констатовано, що НАТО зберігає провідну роль у забезпеченні миру і безпеки в Європі. Відзначено, що перезапуск проекту ЄС з безпеки та оборони після Brexit, президентство Д. Трампа та російська агресія проти України відновила дискусії щодо цілей НАТО після «холодної війни» та про те, як вони пов'язані з ЄС.

Потім стисло розглядається змінне стратегічне середовище, яке сприяє формуванню відносин, включаючи нещодавні пропозиції щодо реалізації заявленого НАТО та ЄС «стратегічного партнерства».

У статті порушене питання лідерства та бачення ролі окремих держав в трансатлантичних відносинах та в питаннях воєнної інтеграції в Європі. Також аналізуються можливості для переведення відносин між НАТО та ЄС на більш конструктивний шлях.

Зазначається, що посилення ЄС своїх амбіцій у сфері оборони та безпеки шляхом розробки Глобальної стратегії ЄС (EUGS) не перешкоджає практичному співробітництву ЄС та НАТО щодо операцій з управління кризами та допомоги у сфері безпеки. Це пов'язано з тим, що європейці поважають зусилля та визнають головну роль НАТО у забезпеченні європейської оборони.

Ключові слова: НАТО, Європейський Союз, співробітництво, трансатлантична безпека, європейська безпека, оборона і безпека.

The paper addresses a range of issues that justify further analytical interaction between the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). It provides a historical background to shape the discussion and describes the evolution of NATO's relations with the European Union. The most important aspects of NATO-EU cooperation in the 21st century are analyzed. The article concludes that there is a trend toward deepening and expanding NATO-EU cooperation in matters of peace and security in Europe. It is noted that NATO continues to play a leading role in ensuring peace and security in Europe. The article also highlights that the relaunch of the EU's security and defense project after Brexit, the presidency of Donald Trump, and Russian aggression against Ukraine have revived discussions on NATO's post-Cold War objectives and their relationship with the EU.

The paper briefly examines the changing strategic environment that fosters the formation of relations, including recent proposals for implementing the declared "strategic partnership" between NATO and the EU.

The issue of leadership and the vision of individual states in transatlantic relations and military integration in Europe is also addressed in the article. Additionally, the paper analyzes opportunities to steer NATO-EU relations in a more constructive direction.

It is noted that the strengthening of the EU's ambitions in the field of defense and security through the development of the EU Global Strategy (EUGS) does not hinder practical cooperation between the EU and NATO regarding crisis management operations and security assistance. It could be explained by the fact that Europeans respect and recognize NATO's primary role in ensuring European defense.

Keywords: *NATO, European Union, cooperation, transatlantic security, European security, defense and security.*

Problem Statement. Transatlantic relations traditionally hold a central place in the agenda for ensuring security and defense in Europe. The complex interactions between Western countries on both sides of the Atlantic ocean regarding the mechanisms for ensuring European defense demonstrate continuity from the start of the discussions around the idea of the parallel existence of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) (1949) and the European Defense Community (1953–1954), the establishment of the Common Security and Defense Policy (1999–2014), and the process of developing EU strategic autonomy, which started in 2016. Some tension in NATO-EU relations at the present stage is linked to the fact that among member states, some countries (mostly Eurosceptics) fear that too overt desire of autonomy by a united Europe will determine U.S. isolationism, while others believe that the U.S. will welcome and take more seriously the European Union that takes itself seriously on matters of its own security and defense. Consequently, the EU fears going too far in matters of its security autonomy so as not to provoke the U.S. Washington, in its turn, seeks to maintain its leadership in ensuring Euro-Atlantic solidarity and therefore does not want to allow a situation where the EU becomes too independent [29].

The main idea of this article is that these at first glance, contradictory ambitions of the Euro-Atlantic integration participants are actually quite compatible: only through its relationship with NATO, and not in opposition to it, the European Union could strive for both autonomy and the strengthening of transatlantic unity.

Assessment of the state of scientific research. Considering the European identity of the Ukrainian people and the irreversibility of Ukraine's European and Euro-Atlantic course, enshrined in the Preamble of the Constitution [4], the research of European and Euro-Atlantic integration is an absolute priority, which is confirmed by numerous publications by both foreign and domestic authors.

Considerable attention is also paid by domestic authors to the study of issues related to Ukraine-EU cooperation (L. Zinyak [3], O. Poshedin [6], Yu. Slyusarenko [8], I. Yakoviyk [14; 36; 37]) and Ukraine - NATO (L. Aleksievets, M. Aleksievets [1], S. Priyduin [7], Y. Stuzhuk, M. Shpura [9]) in the field of security and defense. At the same time, it should be noted that if the problem of NATO-EU cooperation regarding the provision of European defense occupies one of the central places in foreign studies (G. De Maio [18], J. Howorth [24; 25], M. Rutten [30], T. Tardy, G. Lindstrom [32], N. Williams [34]), then Ukrainian authors pay insufficient attention to it (L. Brazhnikova [2], T. Meleshchenko [5], L. Horishko [10], I. Yakoviyk, Ye. Bilousov [11]). This determines the relevance and practical significance of the research.

The purpose of the article is a study based on new documents and modern scientific publications of the formation and development of relations between NATO and the European Union in matters of ensuring peace and security in Europe.

Presentation of the main material. When considering the issue of relations between the European Union and NATO, the following should be taken into account:

– the interaction between the European Communities/EU and NATO is shaped by the fact that most European Communities/EU member states depend on NATO for their own defense. This has an impact on these countries' own perception of the respective roles of the two organizations;

– from the moment when at the end of the 1990s the EU began to demonstrate a desire to play a certain role in security and defense issues¹, the question of its relations with NATO as the main defense player in Europe was quite logically raised. It was far from clear to everyone that the EU is able to do something for the security and defense of Europe that NATO was already doing². Despite existing doubts, at the Washington NATO Summit (1999)

¹The Saint Malo declaration (1998) it states the need for the European Union to «be in a position to play a full role on the international stage. This means making a reality of the Treaty of Amsterdam». However, the declaration also reasserts the primacy of NATO in the European Security architecture: the EU will act in situations where the Alliance is not deployed; the development of the EU capacities must not duplicate NATO's assets [30, P. 8, 9].

²Thus, the US Secretary of State, Madeleine Albright in her famous 3Ds declaration stated: «As Europeans look at the best way to organize their foreign and security policy cooperation, the key is to make sure that any institutional change is consistent with basic principles that have served the Alliance partnership well for 50 years. This means avoiding what I would call the Three Ds : decoupling, duplication and discrimination» [30, P. 11].

Alliance welcomed the recent new impetus for EU's foreign and security cooperation (NATO and the EU should «ensure the development of effective mutual consultation, cooperation and transparency, building on the mechanisms existing between NATO and the WEU»; the EU to «have access to collective NATO assets when acting in crises where NATO is not deployed»[30, P. 22]);

- from the moment of its formation, the European Security and Defense Policy (ESDP) of the EU was conceptualized with NATO crisis management operations as a template. Thus, from the beginning, the EU-NATO relationship was characterized by both complementarity/cooperation and competition in the crisis management market. It is important to note the division of tasks between NATO as a collective defense actor and the EU developing a security agenda short of collective defense³. Yet, in practice, the line distinguishing the respective agendas of the European Union and the North Atlantic Alliance has been difficult to identify, and the EU's desire to play a role in defense has been a source of tensions with NATO.

The NATO-EU cooperation, established in the field of crisis management, is based on shared values, the indivisibility of security, and a determination to address the challenges of the new century, evolving into a strong and mutually beneficial partnership. The relationship between these organizations of a different nature was initiated in the 1990s and received its institutionalization in the NATO-EU Declaration on European Security and Defence Policy (2002) [20]. The Declaration established common political principles and confirmed the EU's access to NATO planning capabilities for its military operations.

In 2003, the "Berlin Plus" agreements laid the foundation for NATO support of EU-led operations in which the Alliance does not actively participate in general [16]. This enabled the European Union to use NATO resources and capabilities for operations in which the Alliance would not be militarily involved. The "Berlin Plus" agreement guaranteed the EU access to NATO planning capabilities, which contribute to EU-led military operations through the identification of command options, procedures for the release and recall of NATO assets and capabilities, and

the exchange of classified intelligence under reciprocal security protection rules. According to N. Williams, "Berlin Plus" offered a sensible compromise to resolve the inherent friction between U.S. demands for its European allies to "do more" in a way that did not undermine NATO, on the one hand, and the ambitions of European countries to play a greater role in their own defense while lacking the means to do so, on the other [34].

Despite the operational practicality and mutually beneficial nature of the "Berlin Plus" arrangements, any new "Berlin Plus" operation faces political obstacles from both NATO and the EU. This could primarily be explained by the fact that "Berlin Plus" was created at a time when the EU lacked sufficient crisis management tools and capabilities. Therefore, NATO's support was considered necessary. Now, aside from large-scale operations, this support is discretionary by nature. Nevertheless, the "Berlin Plus" agreements remain as valid today as they were when first adopted. It should be noted that some elements of "Berlin Plus" are still indispensable, such as the EU having access to capabilities and assets which it does not have and is unlikely to acquire soon—and the EU's military weaknesses could only worsen after Brexit.

The next step was taken at the NATO Lisbon Summit (2010), during which both sides emphasized their desire to enhance the NATO-EU strategic partnership. The Strategic Concept (2010) committed NATO to closer cooperation with other international organizations, particularly the EU, with the aim of preventing crises, managing conflicts, and stabilizing post-conflict situations. One of the key principles of EU-NATO cooperation is the concept of a single set of forces. This means that joint members do not need to have two sets of capability requirements to support each organization, but rather a single set, ensuring efficiency and avoiding duplication [28].

Since 2014, in conditions of increasing geopolitical instability, cooperation between the European Union and NATO has become increasingly important. It is obvious that the security of the EU and NATO are interconnected today: the vast majority of EU member states are NATO allies; together they are also able to mobilize a wide range of tools and use their resources most effectively to address security

³In the Article J.4 Maastricht Treaty (1992) it says: «The policy of the Union in accordance with this Article shall not prejudice the specific character of the security and defence policy of certain Member States and shall respect the obligations of certain

Member States under the North Atlantic Treaty and be compatible with the common security and defence policy established within that framework»[33].

and defense issues. Furthermore, NATO-EU cooperation also contributes to the transatlantic burden-sharing.

The result of the advisory referendum on June 23, 2016, which demonstrated support for the United Kingdom's exit from the European Union, exacerbated the issue of the EU ensuring its own security and defense [12]. In these conditions in June 2016 the EU High Representative presented a new "Global Strategy for the EU's Foreign and Security Policy" [31], which outlined a new approach to a higher level of ambition in the field of security and defense, as well as emphasized the deepening of the EU's partnership with NATO. The Global Strategy framework proposed a number of new mechanisms and tools to address today's complex security challenges, including strengthening cooperation with partners, with NATO being a key one.

Although NATO and the European Union have formally cooperated since 2002, Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014 led the two organizations signed joint declarations in 2016, 2018 and 2023. The value of the documents is primarily symbolic, as they do not contain any announcements or results. In the declarations outlines several key areas for deepened NATO-EU cooperation. The main message is transatlantic unity. In this sense, they reflect the priorities agreed in the Strategic Concept of NATO (the last version of the Concept was adopted in 2022)⁴ and the Strategic Compass of the European Union (2022)⁵.

July 8 2016 p. the President of the European Council and the President of the European Commission, together with the Secretary General of the NATO підписали у Варшаві Joint Declaration in Warsaw with a view to giving new impetus and new substance to the EU-NATO strategic partnership⁶. The NATO-EU strategic partnership received new impetus and substance: 74 specific points of joint action in seven areas were agreed upon⁷, which still serve as the foundation for cooperation between the two organizations. Thus, the Declaration

revitalized the relationship between the two organizations. For the first time in over a decade, this marked a significant step forward in their cooperation.

The goal of this cooperation is to protect a united Europe from unprecedented threats and challenges originating from the East and the South. In this context, NATO and the EU are ideal partners that complement each other. At the same time, the EU's efforts to increase its autonomous defense capabilities objectively strengthen NATO.

To improve the cooperation between the two organizations, informal structures between the EU and NATO were strengthened. While this has improved their relations, they still primarily operate on an ad hoc basis, and staff from both organizations are actively working to address this issue.

It should also be noted that, during this same period, the idea began to be justified that European allies of the U.S. should take responsibility for their own security, as they are more expensive than they are worth.

Taking NATO-EU cooperation to a new level became a shared objective set during the meeting of the North Atlantic Council at the level of NATO foreign ministers with the participation of High Representative/Vice President F. Mogherini in December 2017. During the meeting, the parties concluded that strengthening European defense through permanent structured cooperation (PESCO) and the European Defense Fund would complement NATO's efforts in case if the development of EU and NATO capabilities is consistent.

Three new directions were identified for strengthening NATO-EU cooperation:

- to make military mobility a new flagship of NATO-EU cooperation. It requires: developing procedures for the rapid crossing of our forces and technics across borders; ensuring the reliability of infrastructure, such as roads, railways, ports, and airports; and having an adequate number of transport vehicles⁸;

⁴ Since the end of the Cold War Strategic Concept NATO every 10 years is reviewed and updated, to take account of changes to the global security environment and to make sure the Alliance is prepared for the future.

⁵ The Strategic Compass is an **ambitious plan of action for strengthening the EU's security and defence policy** by 2030. It's an EU security and defence strategy to advance towards a common forward-looking strategic culture as well.

⁶ To support the Declaration, the European Council, the European Parliament and the Commission published the "Statement

on the Implementation of the Joint Declaration" on December 6, 2016.

⁷ The parties agreed on the need to strengthen cooperation in the following seven areas: countering hybrid threats; operational cooperation including at sea and on migration; cyber security and defence; defence capabilities; defence industry and research; exercises; supporting Eastern and Southern partners' capacity-building efforts.

⁸ Ensuring military mobility has become a priority of NATO-EU cooperation in the following years. In 2019, the EU

- to enhance the effectiveness of counterterrorism efforts by improving information sharing between NATO and the EU, as well as coordinating counterterrorism support for partner countries;

- to work together to advance the role of women in peace and security provision.

The parties agreed that implementing joint actions in these areas would take NATO-EU cooperation to a new level, lead to increased defense spending, create more modern capabilities, and achieve a fairer transatlantic burden-sharing [27].

On 10 July, 2018, the President of the European Council and the President of the European Commission, together with the Secretary General of the NATO, signed the second Joint Declaration. The declaration provides that the EU and NATO focus their cooperation on areas such as: military mobility; cyber security; hybrid threats; counter-terrorism; women and security [21].

Thanks to joint efforts, cooperation between the EU and NATO has become the norm and everyday practice and continues to take place on the basis of key guiding principles: openness, transparency, inclusiveness and reciprocity, in full respect of the decision-making autonomy and procedures of both organizations without prejudice to the specific character of the security and defense policy of any Member State.

Bridging the gap between the EU and NATO has become a crucial element in developing a comprehensive international approach to crisis management. During the Brussels Summit NATO Communiqué (2021) [17], although no joint declaration was adopted, two paragraphs of the summit communiqué were dedicated to NATO-EU cooperation:

- §64. «The European Union remains a unique and essential partner for NATO. The NATO-EU strategic partnership is essential for the security and prosperity of our nations and of the Euro-Atlantic area. NATO recognises the importance of a stronger and more capable European defence. The development of coherent, complementary and interoperable defence capabilities, avoiding

provided NATO with updated parameters of its infrastructure, after which the EU Council approved an update of transport infrastructure parameters and geographic data on military needs within the EU and beyond. NATO, in its turn, agreed to public disclosure of its standard for the transportation of dangerous goods to support the EU's work in this area. In 2021, the Alliance transmitted its maps of NATO Main Supply Routes used

unnecessary duplication, is key in our joint efforts to make the Euro-Atlantic area safer. Such efforts, including recent developments, will lead to a stronger NATO, help enhance our common security, contribute to transatlantic burden sharing, help deliver needed capabilities, and support an overall increase in defence spending. ... We will continue to further strengthen our strategic partnership in a spirit of full mutual openness, transparency, complementarity, and respect for the organisations' different mandates, decision-making autonomy and institutional integrity, and as agreed by the two organisations»;

- §65. «NATO-EU cooperation has reached unprecedented levels, with tangible results in countering hybrid and cyber threats, strategic communication, operational cooperation including maritime issues, military mobility, defence capabilities, defence industry and research, exercises, counter-terrorism, and defence and security capacity building. Political dialogue between NATO and the EU remains essential to advance this cooperation. ... The ongoing distinct strategic processes within NATO and the EU offer a unique opportunity to intensify further our consultations and cooperation to enhance the security of our citizens and promote peace and stability in the Euro-Atlantic area and beyond, while reaffirming that NATO remains the transatlantic framework for strong collective defence and the essential forum for security consultations and decisions among Allies».

The crisis associated with the Covid-19 pandemic highlighted the need for deepening cooperation between the EU and NATO through a more complete implementation of the set of 74 specific joint actions outlined in 2016. This is connected with the fact that implementing this set contributes to coherence in addressing evolving security issues such as resilience, new and disruptive technologies, the impact of climate change on security, disinformation, and increasing geostrategic competition. NATO member countries recognized that some current strategic processes within NATO and the EU open opportunities for further intensification of

to move forces and materiel from, though and to allies' territories — to the EU to help ensure coherence and avoid duplication. Because NATO and the EU on similar military forces and capabilities, these maps will allow for stronger synergies between the two organizations. Continuing their co-operation, the respective networks exchanged national points of contact on military mobility. [23].

consultations and cooperation between the two organizations.

Since Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the EU and NATO have intensified their cooperation, demonstrating full unity and joint determination in condemning Russia's brutal aggression against Ukraine and the illegal annexation of parts of Donetsk, Luhansk, Zaporizhzhia, and Kherson regions of Ukraine, as well as supporting the defense of Ukraine and its population. Since February 2022, the European Council and the EU Council have held regular meetings to discuss the situation in Ukraine from various perspectives. At the same time the European Council is ever more steadfast in its support for Ukraine's independence, sovereignty and territorial integrity within its internationally recognised borders, Russia must not prevail [22].

In response to the military aggression, the EU has expanded sanctions against Russia, by adding a significant number of persons and entities to the sanctions list, and by adopting unprecedented restrictive measures [15; 35]. The European Union is determined to continue providing Ukraine and its people all the necessary political, financial, economic, humanitarian, military and diplomatic support for as long as it takes and as intensely as needed [22].

As the security threats and challenges faced by both organizations become increasingly large-scale and significant, NATO and the EU decided to elevate their partnership to a new level based on their years of collaboration. On January 10, 2023, in Brussels, NATO and the EU signed a joint declaration in which they once again condemned Russia's aggression against Ukraine and reaffirmed their unwavering support for Kyiv. The Declaration emphasizes that «NATO remains the foundation of collective defence for its Allies and essential for Euro Atlantic security. We recognise the value of a stronger and more capable European defence that contributes positively to global and transatlantic security and is complementary to, and interoperable with NATO», as well as «they are will further mobilize the combined set of instruments at our disposal, be they political, economic or military, to pursue our common objectives to the benefit of our one billion citizens» [26]. NATO and the EU expressed their readiness to expand and deepen their cooperation in areas such as: the growing geostrategic competition; resilience and the protection of critical infrastructure; emerging and disruptive technologies; space; the security implications

of climate change; foreign information manipulation and interference [26].

The implementation of the joint declaration not seem to require much change in the existing direction of EU-NATO cooperation. Of the joint declaration's 14 clauses, only four contain substantive calls to action; others simply observe changes in the security environment, express principles, or recognize action taken to date. Three of these four points promise a simple change in the degree or intensity of existing areas of cooperation — further strengthen, «expand and deepen», and take to the «next level» the collaboration on agreed issues. This could take any number of forms, from new joint projects to an increase in the intensity and regularity of exchanges between the organizations — or to the more frequent involvement of high-level officials in those exchanges. And only the point on China could be interpreted as laying the foundation for formal EU-NATO cooperation on this new issue [19].

It should be noted that against the backdrop of Russian aggression against Ukraine, both organizations are venturing into such policy areas where they were previously seen as having traditional comparative advantages over each other. For example, NATO aims to play a leading role in hybrid warfare, resilience provision and energy security, while the European Union focuses its efforts on stimulating joint military procurement. As the organizations' areas of competence increasingly overlap, there is an urgent need for closer coordination between them.

Conclusions. The future of EU-NATO relations will primarily depend on the ability of both parties to address a range of interrelated issues. Firstly, it concerns whether transatlantic relations could be improved mainly through the willingness by the US to engage in genuine dialogue with European allies and through rapprochement between France and NATO. Secondly, there is the issue of the resource gap, which underpins the rhetoric of both sides and threatens to undermine the ability of the European Union and NATO to address increasingly complex challenges and security threats in Europe. It should be noted that none of the proposed solutions would be easy to implement. However, if progress is not made, NATO and the European Union risk condemning themselves to growing irrelevance as actors in European security.

NATO and the EU are political and security forums through which member states could engage in defense-industrial cooperation. Each of these

organizations has developed its own unique set of institutional tools to address complex issues such as rising defense procurement costs, technological innovations, defense R&D, standardization, functional compatibility, and more, through which member states are able to manage both the positive effects and negative consequences of globalization in the defense sector.

The question of whether parties on both sides of the Atlantic are moving towards a clear division of work between the EU and NATO on a geographical or functional basis; or the US and Europeans seek to create a fundamentally new balance of

responsibilities and obligations to stabilize European defense and security, remains open today. At the same time, it should be recognized that the "strategic autonomy" of the EU, as envisaged in the document of the Global Strategy (2016), could be achieved only with the Europeanization of NATO itself.

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